

DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL THINKING OF FUTURE TEACHERS USING THE QUASI RESEARCH METHOD

Davletov Erkaboy Yusubovich

Urgench State Pedagogical Institute

Head of the Department of "Physics-Mathematics and Technological Education" d.p.p.s (PhD)

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Abstract: the article describes the problem of developing personal and pedagogical thinking of students in the process of professional training. The criteria and indicators for the development of personal and professional qualities, as well as the parameters of their manifestation, were determined. Examples show the relationship between personal and professional qualities and the requirements of professional standards. The features of the work method as a form of quasi-professional activity are considered. A correlation between formal diagnosis and use as a case assessment tool was established.

Key words: personal qualities, pedagogical thinking, quasi-professional activity, future teachers, work technology, work style.

Introduction:

A modern teacher is a progressive thinker and seeks to see greater freedom of the school in choosing methods of organizing the educational process behind new approaches to the educational system. According to the theory of activity, it is impossible to develop and form the necessary qualities outside of activity. Accordingly, in the educational process, it is necessary to create situations close to the professional activity of future teachers. The purpose of the research: to theoretically justify and experimentally verify the pedagogical conditions for the implementation of quasi-professional activities as a means of developing the personal and professional qualities of future teachers. The object of research: the process of developing the personal and professional qualities of teachers. Research topic: development of personal and professional qualities of future teachers through quasi-professional activities.

Research hypothesis: the development of personal and professional qualities of future teachers through quasi-professional activities will be effective if: based on the integration of psychological and pedagogical literature and theoretical analysis of normative documents, the list and content of these qualities are determined together with students and developed; in the research process, an educational system was developed and applied, which ensures the development of the necessary qualities for students. process of quasi-professional activity; situations defining quasi-professional situations in various subjects are created and used, including methods of analyzing pedagogical situations, mastering methods of professional planning and forecasting aimed at developing personal and professional qualities of future teachers in the process of making pedagogical decisions. The following tasks were solved during the research:

1. Identify theoretical and normative approaches to studying the problem of developing personal and professional qualities of future teachers.

2. *To study the features of quasi-professional activity as a means of developing personal and professional qualities of future teachers.*

3. *To determine the possibilities of Case technology in the development of personal and professional qualities.*

4. *Development and testing of a set of cases defining quasi-professional situations aimed at developing personal and professional qualities of future teachers.*

The methodological basis of the work is as follows: the theory of activity, according to which the assimilation of the content of the studied subject is carried out not by conveying information about it to a person, but in the course of his activity. About objects and events of the surrounding world; the theory of contextual teaching at the university is its flawed characteristic - consistent modeling in the language of science using a system of various forms, methods and tools of the subject and social content of the mastered professional activity; competence-based approach, which reflects a set of general principles of determining educational goals, selecting educational content, organizing the educational process, and evaluating educational outcomes. A set of complementary research methods is used to solve the tasks: theoretical analysis and generalization of psychological and pedagogical literature; psychodiagnostic methods, pedagogical experience.

At the current stage of the development of the educational system, the list of personal and professional qualities of a teacher should be the result, on the one hand, of the theoretical analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature and the integration of normative requirements for a teacher contained in professional standards. On the other hand, the personal and professional qualities of the teacher should help him to carry out his professional activity in accordance with the modern requirements specified in the normative documents. We understand the personal and professional qualities of a teacher as the sum of all socially, biologically and psychologically determined components of a person that predetermine his stable behavior in the professional sphere. Summarizing the approaches to the study of personal and professional qualities, we highlighted a tentative list of personal and professional qualities of a teacher, which are reflected not only in theory, but also in modern normative requirements.

In the process of training future teachers, it is necessary to take into account the requirements for personal and professional qualities of teachers when determining the content and organization of curriculum subjects. This can be done by including quasi-professional activities in science programs. The emergence of quasi-professional activity is connected with the impossibility of transferring the structures of the real professional situation to the walls of the higher education institution.

The process of quasi-professional activity for the development of personal professional qualities in future teachers should include: attitudes, actions, actions of other people that allow the future teacher to evaluate himself as a future specialist in certain professional situations value-semantic analysis; dynamic modeling and prediction of their actions in certain professional situations; evaluation of other people's relationships to their own actions and actions in a real situation that requires the manifestation of personal and professional qualities; problem analysis of achievements made by future teachers in specially modeled pedagogical situations, and then draw a conclusion about the demonstrated qualities; self-study of the personality of the future teacher, which includes the development of the ability to reflect on himself and his qualities in relation to future professional activities; creative

modeling of specific life and professional-pedagogical situations that contribute to the free and full mastery of personal and professional qualities, generalization of this situation into a comprehensive strategy of professional self-development. The method of quasi-professional activity in the process of training future teachers is a practical technology based on solving pedagogical situations, which allows students to establish a real connection between professional knowledge and professional actions in a certain pedagogical situation. . At the same time, an important step in the application of Case technology is the development of specialized cases aimed at developing personal and professional qualities.

During the period of study in higher education, the future teacher will be able to establish a real connection between professional knowledge and professional actions expressed in the ability to purposefully solve this pedagogical situation in a certain pedagogical situation, that is, the context of quasi-professional activity. it is necessary to apply such technologies that determine. The above-mentioned requirements, according to correspond to case technology, which is based on solving pedagogical situations inherent in the content of the work. Downt Case-Tech is a form of quasi-professional activity

Since the process of developing personal and professional qualities is gradual, we have defined a number of criteria and levels of their development. Taking into account a number of mandatory criteria of personal and professional qualities, we distinguished the levels according to each criterion, marking them as intuitive (low), normative (medium), active (high), future we created special cases aimed at developing tolerance and professional responsibility among teachers. The content of each level includes a number of characteristics that allow to assess this level of development of personal and professional quality with maximum accuracy. This is due to the fact that the assessment was based on performance indicators rather than numerical ones. Among the evaluation signs, we noted the following: signs and indicators of effective work on work assignments, characteristics of decisions made by students, guarantees and quality of decisions made as a result of completing work assignments.

The development of personal and professional qualities of future teachers manifests itself in: theoretical knowledge of professional aspects of pedagogical activity; readiness to use different methods of solving difficult situations inherent in pedagogical activity; with the development of the skills of correct interpretation of situations; in mastering the skills of professional forecasting, in foreseeing the possible consequences of the pedagogical decisions made.

Conclusion:

As a result of scientific activity, it has been proven that work technology has an important pedagogical potential as a method of implementing quasi-professional activities: a combination of opportunities to effectively influence the development of qualities. The data obtained in the study confirm the main rules of the hypothesis that we put forward. We do not claim to solve the problem completely. It is possible to continue the research in the direction of creating materials for the development of other personal and professional qualities.

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